

THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA IN INCREASE OF HUMAN VALUES

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Annotation: The article shows that the issue of human destiny and its value is reflected in our national idea, and it is analyzed that it has taken deep roots in the hearts of every person and the whole people living in this country, and has become a spiritual need and a requirement of life.

Key words: Man, human value, destiny, spirituality, social and humanitarian sciences, society, education, training.

РОЛЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИДЕИ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ

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Аннотация: В статье показано, что вопрос о человеческой судьбе и ее ценности находит свое отражение в нашей национальной идее, и анализируется, что она глубоко укоренилась в сердцах каждого человека и всего народа, проживающего в этой стране, и стала духовная потребность и требование жизни.

Ключевые слова: Человек, человеческая ценность, судьба, духовность, социальные и гуманитарные науки, общество, образование, воспитание.

МИЛЛИЙ ҒОЯНИНГ ИНСОН ҚАДРИНИ ОШИРИШДАГИ ЎРНИ

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Аннотация: Мақолада инсон тақдири ва унинг қадри масаласи миллий гоямизда ўз аксини топиши кўрсатиб ўтилган бўлиб ҳозирги кунда шу юртда яшаётган ҳар бир инсон ва бутун халқнинг қалбида чуқур илдиз отиб, унинг маънавий эҳтиёжи ва ҳаёт талабига айланиб кетганлиги тахлил этилган.

Таянч сўзлар: Инсон, инсон қадри, тақдир, маънавият, ижтимоий-гуманитар фанлар, жамият, таълим, тарбия.

The main idea is national statehood, i.e., nationalism, national pride, national unity, which serves development with attention to the essence, increases human value, and creates true patriotism.

Man has been injured so that with the passage of time, his intelligence and thinking abilities began to form. It is the emergence of a person's ability to think that is the biggest reason for him to reach the current level. They became a tribe from a single state, created a state based on their ideas and managed it. All this was to move forward for one goal through one idea and to bring forth individual spiritual qualities among people.

"The national idea is passed down from ancestors to generations, cherished for centuries, deeply rooted in the hearts of every person and the entire people living in this country, and has become their spiritual need and life requirement, so to speak, the noblest dream and hope of any nation. - if we imagine the goals, I think that we will have expressed the essence of such broad concepts.

In fact, we can say that man differs from all other living beings by his intelligence, faith and creative work. One of the ancient rules of philosophy is language and thought. Just as the most primitive product of language is the word, the first form of thought is the concept. Human thinking creates different thoughts, views, ideas and teachings during the perception of reality. But any thought or view, judgment or point of view created by thought cannot be an idea. Only the most powerful, influential, and powerful thoughts can become ideas. One of the differences between ideas and ordinary thoughts is that, although they arise in thinking, they are absorbed into the human psyche, even at the base layers. An idea thus becomes a mental-mental force leading to a moving goal.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis at the end of 2018, our President Shavkat Miromonvich Mirziyoev said: "Today we are moving to the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of the state and society. It's not for nothing, of course. Because in today's fast-paced world, who wins? The state that relies on a new idea, a new idea, and innovation will win. We have huge tasks ahead of us in this direction. The development of our country and the well-being of our people are first of all closely related to the results of our reforms in the social sphere.

As a product of our thinking, an idea emerges in the process of studying the universe. All forms of social consciousness - science, religion, philosophy, art and fiction, ethics, politics and law create certain ideas, rely on them and develop them. In a sense, we can say that each field of consciousness has its own ideas.

Since the days of independence, efforts have been made to define and develop the most basic concepts and principles of our national idea. For this purpose, leading

scientists in the field of social sciences, political scientists and economists, creative intellectuals and the general public began to focus their attention. Taking into account that the age-old dream of our people, the main factor of achieving our goals is related to preservation of independence, its further strengthening and development, the task of determining the meaning and content of our national idea was set based on such criteria, and a number of notable reforms were implemented in this regard.

"Of course, our national idea includes the high concepts of national peace, development of the Motherland, and people's well-being, which embody the noble intentions and vital interests of all people living in this country." The emergence of this or that idea as a national idea is directly related to the past and current state of the nation. After all, relying on these two principles, he can correctly express the goals and tasks that the nation must achieve in the short or long term. Literally, the national idea ultimately had a more or less significant impact on the fate of mankind. Therefore, any national idea has a universal essence. But there are also ideas that are important for a specific nation or for humanity as a whole. For example, let's say that the idea of "National Reconciliation" has a vital meaning for countries that are at war between citizens, while the idea of "Beneficial Cooperation" is equally important for all countries of the world, that is, as it is said, "People unite with each other only for some mutual benefit." At the turning points of its history, each nation first solves the issue of ideology, the problem of forming a social idea that constitutes itself, serves as a unique direction, and a unifying path.

The effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the spiritual sphere of our society is measured by the degree of interdependence of advanced thoughts, ideas, and ideology. Learning the secrets of the universe, discovering the laws of nature and society, natural knowledge and outlook of people are very important in the development of society. In the emergence of scientific knowledge that explained the structure of the world and showed how to live in it, worldly ideas created by the most advanced representatives of humanity have always served for development in their interdependence.

Today, many reforms are being implemented in our country in order to increase the role of spirituality and enlightenment in the way of life of our people. The most important of these are reading reforms, which are being organized in order to further develop the literacy and thinking skills of our people. All this is primarily to increase the value of a person. For example, in a special point of the "Five important initiatives" developed by our president, the priority direction for increasing the effectiveness of reading is defined. And for this purpose, reading events and contests are being organized in every region of our country. This always leads people to perfection.

In the philosophical literature, it is especially noted that the spiritual education of a person is connected with the social and creative-constructive nature of his life, the inclusion of a person in the world of culture. Therefore, only the psychological point of view is limited to a person, which is manifested primarily as a separation and isolation from the breed, its own characteristics and qualities, and the internal interdependence of many psychological abilities and mechanisms. But in fact, the inner world of a person has various connections and relationships with the world of human culture. It is here that he will have a spiritual and moral dimension of the meaning of his life. A person's spiritual life is always focused on others, society, humanity. A person acts in accordance with the highest moral values of human society. Morality is one of the dimensions of human spirituality.

The spirituality of a person is clearly manifested in his unique need and ability to know the world, himself and his place in the world, in his desire to create new forms of social life in accordance with certain laws of human nature. The spiritual searches of a person are especially noted in the products of his artistic-aesthetic activity - literature, visual arts, music and other such creative creations.

Spirituality reflects the general aspects of human life. Spirituality is a complex phenomenon that reflects a person, a subject of mental activity, his personality, his entire cultural and historical life. Spirituality is embedded in the objective world as a trans-subjective, historical interaction and the sum of the activities of countless historical subjects. This process is carried out through specific moral norms and values. From a general cultural point of view, spirituality is not an activity of a subject or a strictly defined norm in society, but a set of conflicting ideal moral norms. Because it would be wrong to consider human spirituality as the content of only the highest examples of human culture (in the form of socio-historical norms and values). Undoubtedly, the assimilation of this content gives and gives a quality identity and clarity to human subjectivity, expands its boundaries, and yet the secrets of a specific, unique soul of a certain person remain. For this reason, the spirituality of a person cannot be clearly revealed through the objective content of even the highest examples of culture that have a common gender. That is, we make sure of its existence. It would be wrong to understand spirituality as a new stage of the complexity of individual mental functions and abilities, "all the functions of the mind are concentrated in a single individuality."

At the current stage of the development of the society, it is very important to have the spiritual superiority of social development, to overcome the spirit of nihilism, passivity, conformism and infantilism, to awaken the desire to fully realize themselves in the minds and hearts of young people. Because it is the youth who are the most

active, sensitive social stratum to internal and external conflicts. That is why it is important to inculcate in the hearts and minds of young people the ideas that inspire optimism, faith in the future and the desire to live for the welfare of neighbors, family, and the Motherland. This process is carried out on the basis of improving spiritual and ideological education. After all, spirituality, with its socio-philosophical basis and level of socio-historical reliability, covers all moral ideal-formative and value-goal relationships aimed at understanding and accepting worldview positions and the meaning of each person's life. It is in this sense that spirituality appears as the main, determining, systematizing and guiding principle of the entire socio-historical process, the cultural life of mankind. Spirituality, after all, determines and mediates external, objective-practical activity, forms and institutions of social relations. Spirituality is the ontological law of society and human development, and social practice is the subject-axiological field of manifestation of spirituality.

List of Used Literature.

1. Санджар, М. Одним из факторов чистоты сердца является Футуват. *Международный журнал инноваций в инженерных исследованиях и технологиях*, 98-101.
2. МУРАДОВ, С. А. СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ФАРИДУДДИНА АТТОРА. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ* Учредители: ООО "Издательство Молодой ученый", (51), 529-531.
3. Мурадов, С. А., & кизи Касимова, Ф. Ф. (2022, December). ФИЛОСОФИЯ ДИЗАЙНА: ОСОБЕННОСТИ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 51-59).
4. Санжар, М. (2020). Взгляды Фаридуддина Аттара на бытие. *Международный журнал прикладных исследований. ИДЖАР*, 6(6), 34-36.
5. Муродов, С. А. (2009). Ибн Сино, Аттор ва Навоий асарларида кушлар тимсоли. *Имом ал-Бухорий сабоқлари», Маънавий-маърифий, илмий-адабий журнал. Тошкент*, 273-276.
6. Мурадов, С. А. Современные методы философии и их значение в развитии мышления человека. *Актуальные исследования*, 51.
7. Murodov, S. A. (2022, November). Relationship between the universe and man in the works of Fariduddin Attor. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 35-41).

8. Karimov, B. K. (2022). HARMONY OF MIND AND SPIRIT. *THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD*, 1(2), 56-61.
9. Каримов, Б. (2011). Гармонизация взаимоотношений государства, общества и человека как основа справедливого общества. постановка вопроса. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 8(1), 71-73.
10. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (2015). Дипломатические и торговые связи Бухары с Россией XVI–XVIII вв. *Молодой учёный*, 20, 548.
11. Мирзакулов, Б. Т. (1994). Рабочая кооперация Узбекистана в 20-е-начале 30-х гг.
12. Султонова, Л. С. (2022). МЕСТО ИНЖЕНЕРНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(6), 29-34.
13. Sultanova, L. (2021). The historical roots of spiritual education of youth. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 461-463.
14. Aminovna, B. G. (2021). The role of social system and political ideas in achieving human prosperity. *Thematics Journal of Education*, 6(November).
15. Аминовна, Б.Г. (2022). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВНУТРЕННИХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ПУТЕЙ СВЯЗИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОАЗИАТСКИХ КОРОЛЕВСТВ В РАЗВИТИИ ТОРГОВЛИ. *Web of Scientist: Международный научный исследовательский журнал*, 3 (10), 12:00–12:05.
16. Темиров, Ш. Т., & Азимов, А. А. (2016). Экономический и культурный рост народов центральной азии в IX-X веках. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 104-105).
17. Jahongir, S. (2020). Philosophical views of Umar life. *Academicia. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.–India*, 10(4), 360-364.
18. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. *International engineering journal for research & development.-India*, 5(3), 143-148.
19. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Interpretation of the image of may in the ruba of Umar Khayyam. *Monografia pokonferencyjna science, research, development*, 33, 2020-30.
20. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём фалсафий қарашларида инсон тақдири ва эркин ирода масаласи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 2, 197-204.
21. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг асосий асарлари ва рубоийларининг тузилиши, мазмуни ва таҳлили. *Илм Сарчаишмалари.-Урганч*, 10, 44-47.

22. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайём рубоийларининг талқин ва тавсифи. *Наманган давлат университети Илмий ахборотномаси*, 9, 206-210.
23. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. (2020). Умар Хайёмнинг ижтимоий-ахлоқий қарашлари. *Фалсафа ва ҳуқуқ.–Тошкент*, 3, 107-110.
24. Shodiev, J. (2021). The problem of knowledge in the philosophical views of Umar Khayyam. *Imam al-Bukhari IBS Journal*, 2.
25. Шодиев, Ж. (2022). Илк уйғониш даврида–комил инсонни шакллантириш ватарбиялашда тасаввуф таълимотининг ўрни. *Scientific Bulletin of NamSU-Научный вестник НамГУ-НамДУ ilmiy axborotnomasi–2022-yil_4-сон*, 229.
26. Шодиев, Ж. Ж. Мамлакатимизда инсон қадрини юксалтиришнинг ижтимоий-фалсафий масалалари. *Қарду хабарлари. Илмий-назарий, услубий журнал. Махсус сон (Ижтимоий фанлар)*.
27. Shodiev, J. J. (2020). INTERPRETATION AND DESCRIPTION OF UMAR KHAYYAM RUBAYA. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(9), 206-211.
28. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). AGAINST IGNORANCE-FIGHTING WITH ENLIGHTENMENT THE MAIN CRITERIA IN IMPROVING HUMAN VALUE. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 1160-1164.
29. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2022). ATTITUDE TO HUMAN DIGNITY IN THE PERIOD OF AMIR TEMUR AND TEMURIDS DYNASTY. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(5), 43-47.
30. Shodiyev, J. (2021). JAMIYATDAGI MEHNAT MUNOSABATLARI SHAROITIDA MA'NAVIY SALOHİYAT. *Журнал истории и общества*, (2)
31. SHODIEV, J. (2021). SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE IN THE PERIOD OF UMAR KHAYYAM. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 1(1).
32. Shodiyev, J. (2021). O'ZBEKISTONDA IJTIMOİY-SIYOSIY KOMMUNIKATSIYA RIVOJLANISHIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SIYOSATI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 409-416.
33. Shodiyev, J. J. (2020). U THE QUESTION OF HUMAN DESTINY AND FREE IN THE PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF OMAR KHAYYAM. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(2), 197-202.
34. Shodiev Jahongir Jurakulovich. Interpretation of moral facts in the opinions of Umar Khayyam. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development* 2020/4/16.

35. Jurakulovich, S. J. (2023). The role of the national idea in increase of human values. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 1160-1164.
36. Shodiyev Jahongir Jo'raqulovich. Inson qadri va uning huquqlari eng oliy qadriyat: tarixiy-huquqiy meros. *Ilm sarchashmalari/ Urganch* – 3.2023. 19-21.
37. Azimov, A. A., & Avliyokulov, U. M. (2019). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ ЭПОХИ АБУ АБДУЛЛАХ РУДАКИ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 560-562.
38. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). Политическая и социальная жизнь в бухарском эмирате во взглядах ахмада дониша. In *Интеграция современных научных исследований в развитие общества* (pp. 66-67).
39. Азимов, А. А., & ўғли Рўзиев, А. Ш. (2022, December). ОСОБЕННОСТИ КНИГИ АВЕСТА. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 37-42).
40. Azimov, A. A. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL AND ETHICAL IDEAS OF THE EARLY RENAISSANCE OF THE EAST IN CENTRAL ASIA AND THEIR REFLECTION IN THE VIEWS OF ZAKARIA AR RAZI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 57-62.
41. Азимов, А. А., & Темиров, Ш. Т. (2016). КУЛЬТУРНАЯ И АРХИТЕКТУРНАЯ ВЗАИМОВЛИЯНИЯ ВОСТОКА И ВОСТОЧНОЙ ЕВРОПЫ С БУХАРОЙ. In *Современные тенденции развития науки и производства* (pp. 33-34).
42. Bafoev, F. M. (2020). О НЕКОТОРЫХ КОНТУРАХ НОВОГО МИРОВОГО ПОРЯДКА: ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ, ПРОГНОЗЫ, ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (12), 388-390.
43. Бафоев, Ф., Мирзаходжаев, А., & Мирзаев, А. (2018). Принцип неделимости безопасности: непрерывность, целостность, универсальность. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 15(1), 80-83.
44. Феруз, Б. (2015). Среднесрочные приоритеты США в Центральной Азии: основы, стимулы, коррективы. *Центральная Азия и Кавказ*, 18(2), 27-37.
45. Бафоев, Ф. М. (2022, November). СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ДАННЫЕ КАК ИНДИКАТОР ЭФФЕКТИВНОЙ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ ЦЕЛЕЙ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ (ЦУР). In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 42-50).
46. Бафоев, Ф. (2012). К ВОПРОСУ ОБ ЭВОЛЮЦИОННОМ ПРИНЦИПЕ СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА НОВОГО ОБЩЕСТВА В НЕЗАВИСИМОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 9(1), 54-55.

47. Bafoev, F. (2019). LIBERAL ISLAM IN THE CONTEMPORARY WORLD: NEW LANDMARKS OF TRUMP'S ADMINISTRATION. *Central Asia & the Caucasus (14046091)*, 20(2).
48. Бафоев, Ф., Мирзаходжаев, А., & Мирзаев, А. (2018). Принцип неделимости безопасности: непрерывность, целостность, универсальность. *Fuqarolik jamiyati. Гражданское общество*, 15(1), 80-83.
49. Феруз, Б. (2015). Среднесрочные приоритеты США в Центральной Азии: основы, стимулы, коррективы. *Центральная Азия и Кавказ*, 18(2), 27-37.
50. Шукуруллаев, Ю. (2022, December). СОЗДАНИЕ ВОЕННЫХ УСТАВНЫХ ГРУПП ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО ТИПА В БУХАРСКОМ ЭМИРАТЕ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 42-51).
51. Шукриллаев, Ю. А. (2006). Бухоро амирлигида кўшин ва ӈарбий иш (1756-1920 йиллар). Тарих фанлари номзоди илмий дражасини олиш учун езилган диссертация.-Тошкент, 2006.
52. Шукруллаев, Ю. А. Армия Бухарского эмирата и военное дело (1756-1920 гг.). Автореферат кандидатской диссертации по истории.-Ташкент, 2006.-26 с.; К вопросу о дипломатических сношениях между Россией и Бухарой через Оренбург в конце XVIII-начале XIX веков. *Общественные науки в Узбекистане*.-1962, 7, 55-59.
53. Ахмеджанов, М. М., & Нурматова, Н. У. (2017). Роль воспитания молодежи в духе толерантности в процессе глобализации. *Молодой ученый*, (7), 421-422.
54. Нурматова, Н. У. (2017). Применение мультимедийных технологий в образовательных учреждениях. *Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука*, (6), 25-27.
55. Ахмеджанов, М. М., & Нурматова, Н. У. (2016). Farabi-first philosopher in his times. *Молодой ученый*, (2), 943-944.
56. ЗОИРОВ, Э. Х. НАУЧНОЕ НАСЛЕДИЕ МАХДУМИ АЪЗАМА. *АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ Учредители: ООО" Агентство перспективных научных исследований"*, (20), 29-32.
57. Зоиров, Э. Х. (2022, December). ДУХОВНОЕ НАСЛЕДИЕ МАХДУМИ АЪЗАМА. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION"* (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 121-131).
58. Zoirov, E. H. (2021). Questions of ontology of nature in the teachings of mahdumi azam. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 91-94.

59. Зоиров, Э. Х. (2022). ОРИФ РЕВГАРИЙ-ВТОРОЙ ПИР БУХОРО-И-ШАРИФ. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(6), 35-43.
60. Khalilovich, Z. E., & Orifovich, D. G. (2020). ANALYSIS OF THE TEACHINGS OF MAHDUMI AZAM AND CLASSIFICATION OF PAMPHLETS. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 5(4), 4-4.
61. Nigmatovna N. G., Erkinovna U. V. Pharaoh of the weavers of bahauddin naqshband // *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 5. – С. 922-926.
62. Наврўзова, Г. (2005). Нақшбандия тасаввуфий таълимоти ва баркамол инсон тарбияси. *Тошкент: “Фан*, 233.
63. Nematovna, N. G. (2021, February). The essence of Abu Ali Ali Sina’s treatise on birds and the influence of mystical ideas on its development. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 19-23).
64. Наврўзова, Г. Н. (2021). Махдуми Аъзам Нақшбандия асоси бўлган тўрт калима хусусида. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 188-199.
65. Наврўзова, Г. Н. (2007). Нақшбандия-камолот йўли. *Тошкент: “Фан*, 189.
66. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномаси.
67. Президент Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Ўзбекистон Республикаси Мустақиллигининг йигирма саккиз йиллигига бағишланган тантанали маросимдаги нутқи.
68. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёев БМТ Бош Ассамблеясининг 72-сессиясида нутқ сўзлади.
69. И.А.Каримов асари-“Юксак маънавият-енгилмас куч”. Тошкент “Маънавият” 2008.
70. “Миллий ғоя ва маънавият” китоби. Абдурахим Эркаев.
71. Ахборот-таълим портали “Миллий ғоя халқ ишончи ва таянчи”.